

Assessing and mapping urban ecological resilience using the loss-gain approach: A case study of Tehran, Iran

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ecological resilience

Spatial assessment framework

Urban Ecological Resilience Mapping (UERM)

ABSTRACT

In the face of growing urban populations and their increasing demand for land and natural resources, the assessment of urban ecological resilience has emerged as an imperative aspect of sustainable urban governance. This study introduces an assessment framework with the potential to substantially augment urban management practices. It is focused on the formulation of a comprehensive framework for assessing ecological resilience, which is applied to Tehran, the capital of Iran. Our proposed Urban Ecological Resilience Mapping (UERM) framework adopts the Loss-Gain approach, encompassing both environmental risks and capacities related to Tehran's urban landscape. This framework incorporates an array of seven distinct indicators and twenty-five variables meticulously designed to gauge the mettle of ecological resilience. The findings underscore that Tehran's central districts exhibit notably low ecological resilience, owing to high population density and the concentration of deteriorated and unstable areas. The localized nature of our assessment framework and its inherent ability to discern spatial dynamics and contributing factors to ecological resilience position it as an indispensable tool for informed urban planning and management decisions. The UERM framework not only facilitates the identification of areas requiring targeted interventions but also empowers urban stakeholders to foster a more resilient and sustainable urban landscape.

1. Introduction

The urban populations growth and urban expansion have led to reduced land use efficiency and habitat degradation, placing pressure on natural resources and the environment's carrying capacity (Tayebi, Alavi, Esfandi, Meshkani, & Shamsipour, 2023). Urban expansion has a fragmenting, isolating, and destructive impact on natural habitats (Astiaso Garcia, Bruschi, Cinquepalmi, & Cumo, 2013; Marzluff, 2001; Potenza, Gerardi, Fascetti, & Rosati, 2022; Zambrano, Aronson, & Fernandez, 2019). It also simplifies and homogenizes species composition (Mironova, Volkova, Gura, & Makar, 2022), disrupts hydrological systems (Arnold & Gibbons, 1996; Tayebi et al., 2022), and alters energy flow and nutrient cycling (Booth & Jackson, 1997; Modrzyński &

Karaszewski, 2022; Wang, Van Dam, Triantafyllidis, Koppelaar, & Shah, 2017). Despite urban areas covering only a small portion of the total land surface (Liu, He, Zhou, & Wu, 2014; UNO, 2018), they consume a significant share of land's carrying capacity in terms of resource and energy consumption, waste generation, and pollutant emissions (OECD G20, 2021; Zheng, Xiao, You, Feng, & Zhiming, 2022). Cities rely on ecosystem services imported from distant regions and depend on global-scale ecological transformations. Changes in the ecological conditions resulting from urbanization, such as watershed pollution, biodiversity loss, and climate change, impact both local and global ecosystem services and ultimately affect the environment's ability to sustain urban populations and infrastructure on a global scale (Alberti & Marzluff, 2004).

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2024.105252>

Received 30 September 2023; Received in revised form 1 February 2024; Accepted 1 February 2024

Available online 10 February 2024

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On the other hand, cities, which house over 4.45 billion people (World Bank, 2023), are increasingly vulnerable to significant natural hazards that pose sudden or gradual threats to public health. These risks are often caused or exacerbated by extensive human-made developments. Cities face multiple challenges such as water scarcity, reduced water quality, and various climate change-related risks like droughts, dust storms, and landslides (Boloorani et al., 2021; Bukhari et al., 2023; Rabbani, Kardani-Yazd, & Mansouri Daneshvar, 2020; Yamagata & Sharifi, 2018). The decisions made regarding urban land use planning, infrastructure investments and control policies can either mitigate or intensify these challenges. The environmental performance of cities has a reciprocal relationship with the regional economy, and this interaction plays a significant role in ecological resilience. Therefore, understanding the ecological resilience of urban systems necessitates studying the sustainable interactions between humans and ecosystems (Costanza, 2020; Hickel, 2020; Maes, Jones, Toledano, & Milligan, 2019). Urban ecosystems offer valuable opportunities to explore and comprehend these sustainable interactions between human activities and ecological processes (Dakas & Kefi, 2022). The significance of cities in achieving sustainability has been acknowledged since the Brundtland report's publication in 1987 (Sharifi, 2021). Subsequently, urban and economic planning and global policy-making institutions have presented various definitions and frameworks to address city resilience and sustainability. Among these frameworks, the most recent and widely referenced is the Sustainable Development Goals, where the eleventh goal explicitly emphasizes the need for actions to enhance sustainability of cities and communities (DESA, 2023; United Nation-HLPF, 2018).

The size and complexity of urban systems have been growing exponentially in the last decades, defying current approaches to sustainable development, so current trends in the development and new functions of urban spaces require innovative and creative approaches to sustainable planning (Botequilha-Leitão & Díaz-Varela, 2020). Ecological resilience refers to the capacity of ecosystems to absorb disturbances, adapt to changes, and maintain their essential functions and services. Ecological resilience, as a concept, plays a crucial role in the global strategies aimed at achieving sustainable development, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The SDGs provide a comprehensive framework for addressing the world's most pressing social, economic, and environmental challenges. Within this framework, ecosystem services and ecological resilience are recognized as a fundamental component for achieving long-term sustainability and resilience at both local and global scales (Chen and et al. 2024; Liang and Li, 2020). By integrating ecological principles into urban planning, cities can contribute to achieving these SDGs. Enhancing urban ecological resilience can help cities mitigate and adapt to climate change, reduce the risk of natural disasters, preserve biodiversity, and improve the overall quality of urban environments (Bush and Doyon, 2019).

Given the simultaneous influence of numerous factors at multiple scales, assessing the ecological resilience of cities requires an interconnected and integrated set of aspects and indicators within a multi-dimensional system. Such a framework can be applied locally in various regions worldwide, considering their distinct economic and social characteristics (Hassanzadehkermanshahi & Shirowzhan, 2022), and can rely on accessible or generable data (Zhang, Wang, Pradhan, Zhao, & Fu, 2022). Furthermore, such a framework should incorporate indicators and criteria that support decision-making and management by city officials. To fulfill this purpose, the framework should demonstrate the dynamics of factors that impact the indicators and enable periodic assessment. Numerous methods have been employed in academia to develop resilience evaluation frameworks, often considering different dimensions of resilience.

Modern cities are facing increasingly complex challenges, and assessing urban sustainability and resilience is crucial to improving their ability to withstand various types of shocks and disasters. Urban resilience and urban ecological resilience are closely related concepts that

focus on the ability of cities to withstand and recover from various shocks and stresses in this matter urban resilience refers to various disruptions from natural to economic and social, and urban ecological resilience is a comprehensive approach which can be defined as the capacity of urban ecosystems to absorb and recover from disturbances while maintaining their essential functions and services. It recognizes the interconnectedness between human and natural systems within cities and aims to promote sustainable and regenerative practices. By doing so, cities can enhance their capacity to withstand disturbances, promote sustainability, and create healthier and more livable environments for humans and nature (Alberti & Marzluff, 2004; Zhang et al., 2023; Zeng et al., 2022; Liu et al. 2024).

In the ever-evolving landscape of urban resilience research, scholars have embarked on diverse journeys to comprehend and enhance the capacity of cities to withstand and recover from environmental and socioeconomic shocks. Asadzadeh, Khavarian-Garmsir, Sharifi, Salehi, and Kötter (2022) provided an extensive overview of the resilience research domain, delineating four prominent areas of focus over the years: vulnerability and climate change adaptation, urban and regional disaster resilience, sustainability management and institutional transformation, and the profound influence of the COVID-19 pandemic. This classification underscores the dynamic nature of urban resilience studies, with researchers continually adapting their approaches to address pressing contemporary challenges (Asadzadeh et al., 2022).

Recent investigations within the realm of urban resilience have manifested the adaptability, unveiling an array of novel dimensions and methodological approaches. Noteworthy contributions include Du, Zhang, Wang, Tao, and Li (2020), who concentrated on quantifying urban land resilience, this study has concentrated on urban land use as a fundamental basis for urban resilience and adaptivity which can lead to land use efficiency, Also Li, Kou, Wang, and Yang (2020), in an effort to develop a framework, harnessed dynamic systems models to fortify urban resilience frameworks. Feng, Xiu, Bai, Zhong, and Wei (2020) explored urban resilience through the lens of landscape patterns, which can be built upon urban environmental capacities and urban planning policies, while Wardekker et al. (2020) innovatively devised policy-making tools for bolstering urban resilience. Meanwhile, McGill (2020) redefined urban resilience with an integrated planning and implementing approach, as a fundamental approach to city management, while Govindarajulu (2020) advocated for augmenting institutional and financial resources to nurture resilient urban landscapes in India. Some studies focus on one dimension of urban system which it's resilience has a dominant effect on the whole system in this case Gonçalves and Ribeiro (2020) probed the resilience of urban transportation systems, additionally some studies like Heinzlef, Robert, Hémond, and Serre (2020) study have a holistic view to the urban system and operationalized urban resilience strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate change (Du et al., 2020; Feng et al., 2020; Gonçalves & Ribeiro, 2020; Govindarajulu, 2020; Heinzlef et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020; Liu & Song, 2020; McGill, 2020; St. George Freeman et al., 2020; Vitale, Meijerink, Moccia, & Ache, 2020; Wardekker et al., 2020).

In the pursuit of comprehending urban ecological resilience, researchers have delved into various dimensions of ecosystems within urban environments. These studies encompass a wide range of ecological elements, including biodiversity conservation, green infrastructure, habitat restoration, and urban ecosystem services. Researchers such as Irfeey et al. (2023) have examined the role of green spaces and urban forests in fostering ecological resilience by promoting biodiversity and mitigating urban heat island effects (Irfeey et al., 2023). Additionally, investigations like Sharifi (2023) have explored the dynamics of urban social-ecological systems, emphasizing the interconnectedness of human communities and their ecological surroundings in urban settings (Sharifi, 2023). Others, like Calliari et al. (2022), have investigated the potential of nature-based solutions and ecosystem-based adaptation strategies to enhance urban resilience by incorporating natural elements into urban planning and design (Calliari et al., 2022). These studies

collectively illuminate the intricate relationship between urban ecosystems and resilience, highlighting the need for tailored methodologies and frameworks, which this paper endeavors to address in the context of Tehran, Iran. seeks to bridge this lacuna by offering a systematic framework for evaluating and enhancing urban ecological resilience. By focusing on Tehran as a case study, this research not only contributes to the broader discourse on urban resilience but also provides valuable insights and strategies for cities grappling with similar ecological challenges.

Given the diverse ecological risks and vulnerabilities present in Tehran, such as thermal loads, air pollution, seismic risk, geological instability, and extensive construction in vulnerable areas, there is a need to develop a framework for assessing the city's ecological resilience. This research aims to investigate the factors that contribute to Tehran's ecological resilience and understand how they interact within a system. Through the identification of contributing factors, an ecological resilience assessment map has been generated as the output of this study. This map serves as a valuable tool for city managers in their urban planning efforts. It can determine the city's capacity for sustainability and assess the degree of environmental vulnerability resulting from both human and natural factors. this study offers solutions to urban managers for enhancing urban resilience against ecological pressures and disturbances. Moreover, this study can serve as a suitable model for ecological resilience assessment in other cities with diverse topographical and climatic characteristics similar to Tehran.

2. Study Area

Tehran, being the political, economic, communication, and service hub of the country, is significantly influenced by global developments and an oil-based economy. The city faces challenges such as excessive population density, concentrated activities, extensive construction, and the physical expansion of urban centers, leading to the destruction of its natural ecosystem. Consequently, Tehran finds itself in an unstable situation in terms of the depletion of ecological resources and facilities and the presence of environmental risks.

Tehran is situated between two distinct ecosystems (Fig. 1), with mountains in the north and desert plains in the south, resulting in a complex ecosystem (Abdoli, Ghahroudi Tali, & TavakoliNia, 2021). The environmental disparities significantly influence the quality of the built-up areas in Tehran. The presence of various ecosystem services in the city has led to the creation of diverse environmental qualities. The central and southern parts of Tehran, located farther from the mountains and closer to the Dasht Kavir desert, are characterized by low and flat lands. These areas experience limited horizontal view, inadequate natural ventilation, and consequently, high levels of air pollution. Additionally, these areas face challenges such as limited average annual rainfall, road flooding, and extremely hot summers (UNDP, 2006).

In contrast, the northern and adjacent areas of Tehran, which border the Alborz Mountain, feature steep slopes and experience wind currents from the mountains to the plains (katabatic) and from the plains to the mountains (anabatic). These areas are known for their more favorable conditions, expansive views, natural landscapes, opportunities for

Fig. 1. (a)Tehran Province in Iran, (b) Tehran city in Tehran Province, (c) Tehran City and the distribution of its green spaces.

mountain recreation, and denser vegetation.

While Tehran is characterized by the presence of diverse ecosystem services, it faces numerous environmental and ecological challenges. These include pollution of water sources, subsidence, floods, landslides, cold waves, frost, soil erosion, heat and humidity stress, water shortage, dust phenomenon, heat waves, high thermal loads, and weak air dynamics capacity. These environmental challenges are further compounded by the significant population residing in Tehran and its surrounding cities, which magnifies the scale and complexity of these issues.

3. Methodology

In recent years, various approaches have been proposed to measure urban resilience, including ecological resilience. These approaches consider different dimensions of resilience, emphasizing balance and growth. Resilience frameworks, such as the Panarchy model, often focus on the dynamics of ecological systems, emphasizing the need to understand thresholds, regime shifts, and adaptive cycles. While valuable, they may lack the specific emphasis on quantifying ecological losses and gains (Kharrazi, Fath, & Katzmair, 2016; Sundstrom et al., 2023). Some studies adopt indicator-based approaches, relying on predefined metrics to assess ecological resilience. While these approaches can provide valuable insights, they may not capture the complexity of urban ecosystems or the trade-offs inherent in urban systems (Linkov, Trump, & Hynes, 2019). Considering the influence of geographical and local conditions on resilience levels, the Among the approaches the Loss-Gain Approach provides a structured and quantitative framework for assessing urban ecological resilience, emphasizing the identification of ecological losses and the potential for gains (Wang, Cai, Xie, Chen, & Zhang, 2023; Zhao, Fang, Liu, & Liu, 2021). By integrating this approach with other spatial analysis tools and indicators, our study aims to offer a comprehensive and adaptable methodology for urban ecological resilience assessment, specifically tailored to the unique context of Tehran, Iran. This combined approach ensures that our framework not only identifies ecological vulnerabilities but also proposes actionable strategies for enhancing resilience in the face of urban challenges. This approach is particularly well-suited to our study for several reasons. Firstly, it aligns with the core objective of assessing and mapping urban ecological resilience, as it enables the quantification of ecological changes within the context of urban development and planning (Chelleri, Waters, Olazabal, & Minucci, 2015; Delgado-Ramos & Guibrunet, 2017). Secondly, the Loss-Gain Approach acknowledges that urban environments are dynamic and ever-changing, and resilience in these settings necessitates not only the protection of existing ecological assets but also the cultivation of new ones (Homayounfar, Muneeppeerakul, & Anderies,). This complements our aim of addressing ecological challenges in Tehran, Iran, by identifying areas where ecological losses can be mitigated and gains can be realized.

In this structured model gain aspect and loss aspect indicators and variables are needed to serve as influential factors and help urban ecological resilience calculation. These factors should be combined in each aspect and be integrated in a final map. Numerous models and methods have been developed to analyze and integrate the factors influencing urban ecological resilience in different cities worldwide (Fu, Liu, Wang, Tian, & Li, 2023; Shi, Zhu, Wu, & Li, 2022; Suárez, Gómez-Baggethun, Benayas, & Tilbury, 2016). These models consider various aspects such as climate, environment, demographics, physical characteristics, cultural factors, urban layout, and infrastructure. In this study, the Urban Ecological Resilience Mapping (UERM) model was developed. This model is inspired by the experimental method of Urban Climate Maps (UCM), which focuses on the relationships between the environment, air, urban climate, and urban morphology. The UCM model, developed based on the work of Professor Knoch from Germany, has been applied in many cities globally and provides context-specific information using local indicators (Ren, Ng, & Katzschner, 2011,

2012). UCM model generates analysis and recommendation maps for urban planning purposes. By combining the indicators and mapping them, this study developed a model for assessment of urban ecological resilience, which helps identify priority areas for enhancing the environmental conditions and any intervention.

The selection of indicators and their corresponding variables for Tehran's urban ecological resilience assessment was based on reviewing policy documents such as Tehran's 5-year urban plans, Tehran's green space master plan and other upstream regulation documents (F, 2021; Madanipour, 2006; Mashayekhi, 2019) as well as related literature via searching in Web of Science and Scopus data bases and selecting unique and highly cited papers; then consultations with researchers and experts (appendix 1) in urban and regional planning and urban environment (22 experts) about the relevancy and meaningfulness of the indicators for Tehran context as well as their priority and weights and data availability.

The UERM model is built upon the integration and presentation of indicators and aspects of urban environmental and ecological resilience. The data collection process focused on obtaining spatial data, and most of the raw data were collected from their original sources. Some data, such as Land Surface Temperature (LST) and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), were processed by satellite images from the OLI sensor of Landsat 8 satellite. Other data, including environmental thermal load, natural ventilation capacity, building volume, Local Climate Zones (LCZ), and Homogeneous Climate Response Units (HCR), were obtained through modeling and integrating raw layers. Additionally, descriptive tables from Tehran Statistical facts, the Air Quality Control Center, and Water Organization of Tehran were used to extract spatial information layers (Table 2).

The integration of layers in the model follows the pairwise comparison approach according to the process of hierarchical analysis based on the degree of preference from 1 to 9 (Allahi, Mobin, Vafadarnikjoo, & Salmon, 2015). So that the number 1 indicates the equality of two variables and the number 9 indicates the highest degree of preference. To determine the importance of each criterion compared to the other, a matrix was drawn and their weighting was done based on expert opinion. All information layers were made dimensionless based on the coefficients obtained from the previous step; In the next step, all of them were converted into a raster format by determining the same coordinate system. Finally, by applying the coefficients obtained from prioritizing the criteria, the information layers were integrated. To avoid calculation errors during the simultaneous integration of layers, three stages of layer integration were applied. In the first stage, the seven indicators described in the third column of Table 1 these seven ecological indicators were combined to calculate two aspects: 1) environmental capacities and services, and 2) environmental risks and hazards. The indicators were divided into two aspects according to their positive or negative effects on ecological resilience. Finally, by combining these two aspects, the classification map of Tehran's urban ecological resilience was calculated in the third stage. Fig. 2 describes the research process according to what was said.

4. Results and discussions

The spatial pattern of urban ecological resilience in Tehran depends on various factors such as its geographical features like complex topography on the southern foothills of the Alborz mountains range, geomorphology and arid climate with water shortage; as well as its presence and distribution of parks, gardens, and other green spaces especially the middle belt of open and green spaces stretched in the east-west direction of Tehran city. Under the influence of environmental conditions and arid climate, the city of Tehran has a compact form in an area equal to 615 square kilometers, which is one of the largest cities in West Asia and the 27th largest city in the world, with a population of about 9 million and a population density of 13,800 people per square kilometer, is in the 15th rank of dense cities in the world (Shamsipour,

Table 1

The structure of variables, indicators and aspects of Tehran's urban ecological resilience assessment.

Goal	Aspects	Indicators	Effect	Variables	
Tehran's urban ecological resilience map	Environmental Capacities and services GAIN	Carbon sequestration and storage capacity	+	Green Spaces	(Cardoso et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2023; Datola, 2023a; Phillis, Kouikoglou, & Verdugo, 2017)
			+	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	(Alcoforado, Andrade, Lopes, & Vasconcelos, 2009)
		Natural ventilation capacity	+	Linear green spaces	(Phillis et al., 2017)
			+	Urban road network (air flow corridors)	(Li & Yi, 2020)
			-	Building Density	(Sharifi, 2019)
		Natural Landscape	-	Land Cover	(Cardoso et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2023; Chen, Jiang, Xu, Xu, & Guan, 2023; Datola, 2023)
			+	Proximity to green and open spaces	(Li & Yi, 2020)
			+	The Network of water channels and streams	(Li & Yi, 2020)
			+	Green Spaces	(Cardoso et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2023; Datola, 2023; Phillis et al., 2017)
			+	Natural urban morphology	(Shen, Kylo, & Guo, 2013)
	environmental risks and hazards LOSS	Environmental Thermal Load	+	Topography	(Chen et al., 2023)
			-	Volume of buildings	(Feofilovs & Romagnoli, 2020)
		Surface impermeability ratio	-/+	Homogeneous Climate Response Units (HCR)	(Alcoforado et al., 2009; Ullah, Akbar, & Khan, 2020)
			+	Proximity to green and open spaces	(Cardoso et al., 2020)
			-	Building density	(Sharifi, 2019)
		Air pollution	-/+	Population Density	(Cardoso et al., 2020; Datola, 2023)
			-	Built-up area ratio	(Cardoso et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2023; Datola, 2023)
		Risk with biophysical factors	-/+	Local Climate Zones (LCZ)	(Alcoforado et al., 2009; Chen et al., 2023)
			-/+	Urban Land Use	(Cardoso et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2023; Feofilovs & Romagnoli, 2020)
			-	PM Emission	(Chen et al., 2023; Feofilovs & Romagnoli, 2020; Sharifi & Yamagata, 2016)
-	Emission CO		(Chen et al., 2023; Feofilovs & Romagnoli, 2020; Sharifi & Yamagata, 2016)		
-/+	Ground Water Level		(Chen et al., 2023; Li, Lin, Li, & Nyerges, 2019)		
		Faults	(Abedini, Aram, Khalili, & Mirzaei, 2022; Anelli, Tajani, & Ranieri, 2022)		
		Land Surface Temperature (LST)	(Alcoforado et al., 2009; Qiao et al., 2023; Tayebi et al., 2019)		
		The Network of water channels and streams	(Chen et al., 2023; Chen et al., 2023; Li et al., 2019)		

2022).

Due to the height difference of over 1000 meters between the south and the north of the city, there are various air temperature, humidity and wind conditions. The northern parts of the city are characterized by denser vegetation, mild weather, and more rainfall compared to the hot and drier southern parts. The ten gorges in the northern side of the city are the corridors for fresh and cool air flow from Alborz mountain into the city. The high density of buildings and activities in the downtown is the main reason for the high thermal loads and the concentration of the urban heat island, habitat fragmentation and air pollution.

In this section, the analysis focuses on the outcomes of seven indicators and their corresponding variables. Subsequently, two aspects, first environmental capacities and services, and second environmental risks and hazards are analyzed. Lastly, an assessment is conducted on the classification map of ecological resilience in Tehran.

4.1. Environmental capacities and services

4.1.1. Carbon sequestration and storage capacity

Cities play a significant role in climate change mitigation (Churkina, 2016). In Tehran, a city constrained by limited natural and soil land resources, urban green spaces emerge as vital carbon sinks, facilitating the storage and deposition of atmospheric carbon. Our assessment of Tehran's carbon sequestration and storage capacity reveals that approximately 28% of the city's total area, encompassing open and agricultural spaces, and an additional 22% consisting of forest parks and urban green areas, possess notable potential for carbon sequestration.

Notably, a spatial analysis unveils a dearth of green and open spaces within the central districts, the historical core of Tehran. Consequently, northern districts, particularly districts 4, 22, 18, and 2, exhibit favorable conditions for carbon sequestration due to their abundance of trees and vegetation, whereas central districts such as 10, 11, 12, and 7 depict unfavorable conditions in this regard (See Fig. 3a).

4.1.2. Natural Ventilation Capacity

Natural ventilation is an effective approach to mitigate the adverse impacts of urban heat, reduce energy consumption, and decrease air pollution (Saif, Wright, Khattak, & Elfadli, 2021). In Tehran, during the hot and dry summer months, airflow is crucial in reducing heat stress and enhancing thermal comfort. Similarly, in colder months, it aids in moderating and eliminating urban pollution. The natural ventilation of urban air is a significant indicator of ecological stability and resilience. This indicator is influenced by various factors such as land cover type, building height and density, road networks, and proximity to green spaces. The results obtained from the dynamic mapping of Tehran's natural ventilation capacity indicate that over 41% of the city exhibits no airflow capability. This outcome can be attributed to the high concentration of buildings in the central, eastern, and northeastern districts. Less than 30% of the city demonstrates relatively favorable air movement conditions, primarily in District 9 (Mehrabad airport area), 18 and 19 (agricultural fields), and District 22 characterized by barren and open lands. However, it is important to note that District 22 is currently undergoing extensive construction, impacting its status. Consequently, these areas also exhibit moderate to average conditions in terms of

Table 2
Data and sources.

	Layer Name	Layer Type	Scale	Source
1	Urban Green Spaces	Vector	1:10000	Tehran Municipality
2	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)	Satellite Image	50 meters	Landsat 8
3	Urban Roads	Vector	1:10,000	Tehran Municipality
4	Building Density	Vector	Neighborhood	Tehran Municipality
5	Land Cover	Raster	50 meters	Calculated by Authors
6	Near to Urban Green space	Scalaire Data	50 meters	Calculated by Authors
7	Water Streams and rivers	Vector	1:10000	Tehran Municipality
8	Topography	Scalaire Data	10 meters	Iran National Cartographic Center
9	Construction Volume	Scalaire Data	50 meters	Calculated by Authors
10	Homogeneous Climate Response Units (HCR)	Vector	Tehran and surrounding	Calculated by Authors
11	Population Density	Vector	Neighborhood	Tehran Municipality
12	Built-Up area Ratio	Scalaire Data	50 meters	Calculated by Authors
13	Local Climate Zone	Satellite Image	50 meters	Calculated by Authors
14	Urban Land Use	Vector	1:10000	Tehran Municipality
15	Urban Municipal districts	Vector	Neighborhood And Districts	Tehran Municipality
16	Spatial distribution of PM Emission	Attribute Table	Neighborhood	Tehran Municipality
17	Spatial distribution of CO Emission	Attribute Table	Neighborhood	Tehran Municipality
18	Ground water Level	Attribute Table	Tehran Plain	Water Organization of Tehran
19	Faults	Vector	1:10000	Tehran Municipality
20	Land Surface Temperature	Satellite Image	50 meters	Landsat 8

dynamic ability and air conditioning capacity (Fig. 3b).

4.1.3. Natural Landscapes

This indicator assesses how the city's topography, influenced by nearby mountains, rivers, and valleys, shapes natural landscapes. In Tehran, where the presence of mountains and water features is significant, this indicator incorporates variables such as topography, natural urban morphology, water channels, and urban green spaces. Desirable and valuable natural landscapes, comprising roughly 15% of the total area, are predominantly situated in the city's outskirts. Notably, Tehran's northern mountains, rivers, and groves emerge as the most prominent natural landscapes and green spaces. Moreover, the city's green and recreational riverbeds constitute approximately 30% of the total area, representing significant artificial landscapes. It is worth noting that a discernible trend indicates a decline in landscape quality from north to south within Tehran (See Fig. 3c).

4.1.4. Total Environmental capacities and services

The positioning of Tehran between the mountainous and desert has given rise to diverse environmental conditions. This location has resulted in a variety of environmental phenomena and characteristics in Tehran. The presence of variations in altitude is responsible for extensive environmental changes, including temperature differences and

pressure gradients that facilitate airflow. One significant challenge faced by large cities is inadequate natural ventilation, which, in Tehran's case, contributes to the accumulation of pollutants and worsens air quality (Tayebi et al., 2019). However, the differences in altitude offer the opportunity to supply cool and fresh air to urban areas. Additionally, the upstream watersheds receive more precipitation and nourish the rivers and aquifers of the Tehran plain. The cultural and recreational facilities in the Tochal mountain area provide further environmental benefits for citizens. The differences in altitude also offer a wide range of natural landscapes for the city's inhabitants to enjoy. The only positive point about southern part of the city is that, the plain area to the south of Tehran acts as a reservoir for the underground water of the Tehran plain due to variations in height and slope in its hydrology and surface. The water level in this area is closer to the surface and exhibits greater capacity for water harvesting. As a result, agricultural and garden lands have expanded in this area, supplying food (such as vegetables and fruits) to the city's residents. In cumulating with all indicators consequently, the northern boundaries of Tehran contain the maximum extent of Class 5, which indicates high environmental capabilities and services, while the ecological capacity of lands decreases as one moves southward (Fig. 3d).

In summary, approximately 15 percent of the city's total area possesses the capacity to offer favorable and moderately favorable ecological services. These services predominantly arise from the presence of green spaces, groves, lakes, and riverbeds. It is important to note that these figures specifically pertain to the city of Tehran, excluding the area of the northern heights. On the other hand, approximately 60 percent of the city's area is characterized by unfavorable conditions, primarily due to densely constructed spaces with a fine-grained pattern (Table 3).

4.2. Environmental risks and hazards

4.2.1. Environmental Thermal Load

The environmental thermal load indicator assesses the intensity of heat storage or emission in specific locations within urban areas. Factors influencing thermal load include the volume of buildings (which affects heat storage, limited sky view, and reduces nighttime cooling), topography, and accessibility to green spaces, which provide a cooling effect (Tayebi et al., 2023). Essentially, the thermal load considers how various factors can raise or lower the urban air temperature. It refers to changes in air temperature within the city caused by different urban forms and surfaces. The primary issue associated with urbanization is the thermal load generated by artificial structures and surfaces. Thermal load is considered the key contributor to increased temperatures within the city. In Tehran's hot and arid climate, thermal load exacerbates heat stress during summer months, making outdoor conditions less comfortable for residents. Additionally, energy consumption in buildings significantly increases. The results obtained from the environmental thermal load map indicate that less than 5% of the city's area experiences very high environmental thermal load, while over 63% exhibits moderate conditions. When including areas with moderate cold and hot levels, more than 78% of the city area demonstrates moderate environmental thermal load conditions. It is important to note that 23% of the area experiences cold conditions, while 18% of the city is characterized by high heat. The possibility of air exchange between these different zones can be facilitated and measured by creating ecological passages and highways in a north-south direction (Fig. 4a).

4.2.2. Surface Impermeability Ratio

In many contexts, rapid urbanization has resulted in the conversion of extensive agricultural areas, pastures, and meadows into residential, industrial, and other infrastructure spaces. The primary consequence of covering natural soil with concrete, asphalt, and paving stones is the creation of impermeable surfaces, which negatively impacts both the water cycle and surface energy balance. Tehran's central, eastern, and northern areas exhibit a dense urban fabric with limited permeable

Fig. 2. the study methodological framework.

surfaces, indicating a scarcity of green and natural spaces. Among the districts, Districts 6, 3, and 4 display the lowest permeability coefficient (less than 10%), while Districts 19, 18, and 21 exhibit the highest percentage of permeability (ranging between 40 and 50%). The central and eastern districts also show unfavorable conditions, with permeability levels below 20%. Consequently, less than 5% of the city and its immediate suburbs have a permeability rate of less than 10. As a result, the surrounding suburbs of Tehran, particularly in mountainous regions, have the potential for water infiltration through rainfall, contributing to the replenishment of the Tehran plain's aquifer. In the southern side of the city, the permeability coefficient is approximately 70%, indicating the potential for water absorption by plant roots and supporting agricultural and horticultural crops. The calculation of this indicator incorporates various layers, including building levels, building density, and Local Climate Zones (LCZ) of Tehran.

4.2.3. Air Pollution

The northern neighborhoods and districts of Tehran exhibit high levels of carbon monoxide emissions, while the southern districts have relatively higher levels of particular matters (PMs). The central and southeastern areas experience significant emissions of pollutants. In the western part of Tehran, pollution is primarily attributed to the concentration of silos, warehouses, and various active factories. In the eastern and the southern areas, industrial pollutants, such as cement production and other fixed sources, contribute to air pollution. Conversely, pollution in the central areas of the city is predominantly caused by traffic and mobile sources. Overall, 63 neighborhoods in Tehran, covering an area of over 152 square kilometers, face an unfavorable and vulnerable ecological situation due to the annual emission of more than 400 tons of pollutants. On the other hand, 40 neighborhoods, mainly located in the northern and western suburbs of the city, exhibit a comparatively better situation, with emissions below 100 tons

Fig. 3. Environmental Capacities and services aspect, 3a. Carbon sequestration and storage capacity, 3b. Natural ventilation capacity, 3c. Natural landscapes and 3d. Environmental Capacities and services.

Table 3
Classes, area and percentage of Tehran’s Environmental Capacities and services.

Classes	Area (KM2)	Percentage	Practical aspect
Class 1	119.83	19.82	Un- Favorable ecological services
Class 2	242.39	40.1	moderately un-Favorable ecological services
Class 3	160.28	26.52	Average ecological services
Class 4	78.37	12.97	moderately Favorable ecological services
Class 5	13.19	2.18	Favorable ecological services
	614.06	100	

per year. The combined layers used to calculate this indicator include annual emissions of suspended particles, carbon monoxide, nitrogen oxides, and volatile organic compounds.

4.2.4. Risk with biophysical factors

Regarding this indicator, four selected variables were calculated and mapped. Less than 4% of Tehran and its suburbs have been identified as high-risk areas, mainly located in flood-prone zones. These areas are characterized by factors such as river flow, prohibited fault boundaries, significant drop in groundwater levels, and high surface temperatures. On the other hand, over 52% of the assessed area exhibits low and relatively low levels of risk, primarily scattered in the outskirts of the city. It is important to note that all 57 square kilometers with high-risk ratings are concentrated within the city limits, particularly in the northern areas of Tehran. Due to the mountainous nature and active tectonic zone of this region, as well as the presence of valleys and rivers that outlet in the northern areas, the risk factors are elevated in these areas. Consequently, the highest risk values are observed in these northern districts.

4.2.5. Total Environmental risks and hazards

The city of Tehran, located at the base of the Alborz mountains, possesses an active geo-structural structure that has led to the formation of fractures and active thrust faults surrounding the city (Kamranzad, Memarian, & Zare, 2020). These faults pose a significant earthquake hazard, with Tehran being entirely susceptible to their pressure from the north and south. In addition to the primary faults in the outskirts of the city, there are secondary but active faults, particularly in the northern strip of Tehran, highlighting the environmental-geo-structural danger of the region. The heights dominating the northern side of the city serve as the catchment areas for occasional heavy rains and floods, which have caused flooding incidents in Tehran on several occasions (such as the August 1985 Tajrish flood and the August 2022 floods in Imamzadeh Dawood and Firouzkoh) (DAVIES, 2022). Therefore, the occurrence of extreme rainfall and floods represents one of the environmental hazards in the area, capable of causing significant floods and damaging urban infrastructure. Despite the steep slopes in the northern strip of Tehran, the central and southern parts of the city, located on the plain, have very low surface slopes. These parts, which cover a large portion of Tehran’s center and south, exhibit a high potential for road and neighborhood flooding. Even a few millimeters of rain can lead to a flood crisis in many neighborhoods. Furthermore, the dense urban structure, particularly in the central and northern parts (such as Districts 6, 3, 12, and the southern part of District 2), limits sky visibility and traps solar radiation due to its irregular geometry. During the night, these areas hinder the dissipation of ground energy and, coupled with reduced wind intensity, significantly contribute to the intensification of environmental thermal load. The central and eastern areas of the city show unfavorable conditions in terms of air pollution and heat load due to the compactness of the fabric, lack of green spaces, high density of construction, population and activity. These areas are the main area and core of Tehran’s urban

4a

4b

4c

4d

4e

Fig. 4. Aspect of environmental risks and hazards, 4a. Environmental thermal load map, 4b. Surface impermeability ratio map, 4c. Air pollution map, 4d. Risk with biophysical factors.

heat island (Moghbel & Shamsipour, 2019). These issues are caused by the weak natural ventilation of the central areas of the city, which is determined by the measure of permeability. According to the results obtained from the analysis of the urban fabric of Tehran, the areas of the center have been identified with an aging penetration rate of less than 10%. While this value is between 40 and 50 percent for the western and northwestern regions. In general, Tehran is known as a city with compact texture, where the permeability coefficient and air flow displacement are weak. Therefore, the main strategy to reduce air pollution and reduce the intensity of the urban heat island is to create west-east corridors corresponding to the direction of the west or north-south winds, corresponding to the direction of the mountain

katabatic winds along the highways.

The environmental hazard map of Tehran, as presented in Table 4,

Table 4
Classes, area, and the percentage of Tehran’s environmental risks and hazards.

classes	Area (KM2)	Percentage	Practical Aspect
Class1	72.97	11.88	Low Risk
Class2	177.62	28.93	Semi High Risk
Class3	153.17	24.92	Average Risk
Class4	122.67	19.98	Semi High Risk
Class5	87.63	14.29	High Risk
	614.06	100	

reveals that approximately 15% of the city is at high or relatively high risk, primarily concentrated in areas 6, 7, 2, 12, and 3. Additionally, approximately 20% of the city is classified as low risk (Table 4).

4.3. Total Ecological resilience

Following the calculation of indicators and aspects, an ecological resilience assessment map of Tehran has been prepared by combining the mentioned aspects. The city, with its diverse environmental and topographic characteristics, exhibits varying conditions in the provision of ecosystem services. Due to the absence of coherent planning and specific patterns in the development of man-made spaces, the state of urban resilience, particularly in ecological and environmental aspects, fluctuates and varies across different areas. These conditions may not be evident or fully understood through a general overview of Tehran, highlighting the importance of considering the spatial variability and angles involved.

The final outcome resulted from integrating 25 environmental and urban layers into 7 indicators and two management aspects is depicted in Fig. 5. The classification map represents the level of ecological resilience in Tehran. According to the figure, the central areas of Tehran exhibit weak resilience. The district with the highest resilience is District 22, where a significant portion is characterized by high resilience. District 1 demonstrates a favorable ecological resilience situation. Districts 9 and 19, as well as the northern parts of Districts 2 and 5, are characterized by favorable ecological resilience. On the other hand, the central districts, including Districts 10, 11, 12, 6, and the southern part of Districts 2 and 7, present the worst resilience situation. These districts are marked by high environmental thermal load, dense urban texture, high building density, limited natural ventilation, lack of dynamic potential, scarcity of expansive natural landscapes, and inadequate green spaces, resulting in low ecological resilience.

According to Table 5, only 6.64% of the city’s area exhibits favorable and high ecological resilience. These areas, covering less than 40 square kilometers, consist of green infrastructures, particularly large forest parks that stretch in a west-east direction across the northern half of the city. Additionally, the riverbeds and valleys play a significant role in enhancing ecological resilience. For example, Nahj-ul-Balagha Park in Farahzad Valley features extensive green and recreational spaces, while some areas like Derke and Darband neighborhoods have maintained high ecological resilience despite being densely built-up.

Table 5

Classes, area, and percentage of Tehran’s Ecological Resilience map.

Classes	Area (KM2)	Percentage	Management Aspect
Very Low Resilience	74.93	12.2	Urban areas with high building and population density
Low Resilience	178.47	29.07	Urban areas with relatively high building density and population
Average Resilience	131.97	21.46	The in-city green spaces and small open spaces
High Resilience	189.3	30.63	The in-city Open and green mixed spaces
Very High Resilience	39.34	6.64	Dense green infrastructures inside and in the suburbs of the city
	614.06	100	

Over 30% of the city’s area displays a relatively good level of resilience, characterized by urban open spaces, airport areas (such as Mehrabad, Dushan-Tepe, and Bostan Velayat), and agricultural and barren lands in the southern edge of the city, specifically in District 19. Despite facing environmental challenges and air pollution, these areas are ecologically significant due to the presence of open spaces that contribute to air conditioning, low environmental thermal load, appealing landscapes, and a low ratio of impervious surfaces. More than 12% of the city’s area, approximately 75 square kilometers, exhibits very low resilience, indicating not only the absence of adequate environmental services and capabilities but also the presence of significant risks and hazards. This low resilience level can be observed predominantly in the central areas of the city.

According to (Meerow, Newell, & Stults, 2016), the concept of urban resilience encompasses six basic elements: (1) defining the urban context, (2) understanding system equilibrium, (3) considering positive versus neutral/negative conceptualizations of resilience, (4) identifying mechanisms for system change, (5) balancing consistency versus general consistency, and (6) determining the time frame for action. It is crucial to consider resilience at intra-urban scales, as cities are composed of various interconnected yet sometimes scattered areas. A true mechanism cannot be attributed to the city as a system if its elements do not play a role in that mechanism. Moreover, maintaining and improving balance and setting priorities for actions, including adaptive change and management planning within municipal limits, hold significant importance. Therefore, evaluating inner city areas and assessing them in terms of

Fig. 5. Classification of ecological resilience of Tehran city.

various resilience dimensions is particularly meaningful(Cao, Wilkin-son, Pettinotti, Colenbrander, & Lovell, 2021).

Referring to Fig. 5, it is evident that except for certain areas in the northern strip of Tehran (Districts 22, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6) where a portion of these areas exhibit high resilience, the remaining districts, particularly in the central, south, and east of Tehran, demonstrate limited levels of resilience. Although all these districts lack ecological resilience, the reasons for their low resilience differ. In the central areas, the high density of construction, activities, and traffic contribute to increased heat stress, diminished natural air ventilation, aggravated air pollution, extensive land cover/land use changes, a high percentage of impervious surfaces, and the fragmentation of natural habitats (leaving no remaining natural habitats). These factors are the primary drivers behind the reduction in resilience in these areas.

On the other hand, in the peripheral areas of Tehran, particularly in the south, the lack of ecological infrastructure, absence of natural landscapes and green spaces, heat stress, air pollution, aridity, and the absence of services and ecological focal points have contributed to the dominance of levels with weak and very low resilience.

Fig. 6 shows that over 75% of the central areas of Tehran (including Districts 10, 11, and 12) are characterized by low and very low ecological resilience. District 12 has the worst situation, with over 83% of its area exhibiting low resilience, followed by District 10, with approximately 77% of its area in the same category. These areas are densely populated, characterized by worn-out urban fabric, and are in need of intervention based on local development plans (Hajialiakbari, Karimi, & Tayebi, 2021). The low resilience of these areas can be attributed to factors such as high impervious surface ratio, high construction and population density, lack of green infrastructure, formation of urban heat island phenomenon, limited natural ventilation, severe air pollution, and absence of natural landscapes.

On the other hand, Districts 1 and 22 on both sides of the northern strip of Tehran exhibit the best environmental (ecological) resilience. The presence of abundant green infrastructure, accessibility to natural landscapes such as the Alborz Mountain, river valleys, and forest parks, favorable conditions for natural air ventilation, and low air pollution contribute to their high level of ecological resilience. Additionally, Districts 18 and 19 demonstrate relatively good resilience, with garden and agricultural lands, open spaces, low construction and population density, and minimal environmental pollutants. In summary, the resilience decreases from the peripheral areas towards the center, with the central and old areas of Tehran exhibiting weak and very weak resilience.

The district-scaled assessment of resilience in Tehran, alongside the overall resilience of the city, serves as a decision-making tool to determine priorities for action in different districts. This tool emphasizes the importance of balanced resilience within the defined limits of the city as a measure of action priority (Tayebi, Esfandi, Bahraini Moqadam, & Sharifi, 2022). These results are utilized in urban planning and the formulation of strategic plans for cities (Jha, Miner, & Stanton-Geddes, 2013; Li, Cheng, & Wu, 2022; Yang, Jiao, & Zhang, 2022; You, Sun, & Liu, 2022).

5. Conclusion

Rapid urbanization, coupled with the disregard for ecological aspects, presents numerous challenges and problems. These include the depletion of natural resources, environmental pollution, disruption of the urban ecosystem’s metabolism due to excessive consumption of substances and energy, population congestion, increased urban traffic, inadequate open and green spaces, land use changes, regression of ecosystems, air and water pollution, and increased waste production. These issues indicate the mounting pressure exerted by humans on urban ecosystems and the excessive demand for urban resources, posing a significant threat to their resilience.

In general, the intensifying pressure on the carrying capacity of urban ecosystems leads to instabilities in four areas: urban services and facilities, environmental degradation, scarcity of natural resources, and social problems. It is essential to ensure that development strategies and investment decisions in cities are oriented towards enhancing urban resilience rather than diminishing it. Consequently, urban resilience planning and management have become crucial. Effective resilience management necessitates understanding thresholds, identifying their characteristics, adjusting thresholds when feasible, and preventing systems from reaching thresholds that result in undesirable situations. Such knowledge should stem from a flexible and context-oriented framework that evaluates the dynamics of urban resilience.

This study examines 25 indicators related to urban resilience, focusing on environmental services, ecological resources, and the environmental risks associated with these resources in Tehran and its suburbs. By combining various layers of information, the study provides insights into the city’s ecological resilience. The results indicate a low and very low level of resilience in the central areas of Tehran, which coincides with high population density and the concentration of aging and unstable urban areas. The low resilience observed in these areas can be attributed to indicators such as a high proportion of impervious

Fig. 6. the resiliency of Tehran’s 22 districts (percentage of Area).

surfaces, high building and population density, inadequate green infrastructure, the formation of the urban heat island phenomenon, limited natural air ventilation, severe air pollution, and a lack of natural scenery.

On the other hand, Districts 1 and 22, situated on opposite sides of the northern strip of Tehran, exhibit the highest level of ecological resilience. This high resilience can be attributed to factors such as abundant green infrastructure, accessible natural landscapes (such as the Alborz Mountain, river valleys, and forest parks), favorable potential for natural air ventilation, and low levels of air pollution. Districts 18 and 19 also display relatively good resilience. These areas, located in the south of the city, are characterized by gardens and agricultural lands, open spaces with low construction and population density, and minimal environmental pollutants. In other words, resilience decreases from the peripheral areas towards the city center, with the central and older areas of Tehran showing weak and very weak levels of resilience.

The assessment of ecological resilience in Tehran by districts, as well as the overall assessment of the city's resilience, serves as a valuable decision-making tool. It assists in determining priority actions and interventions in different districts of the city. This tool can influence urban development patterns, the planning of green spaces, the prioritization of revitalizing deteriorated areas, public transportation planning, and the implementation of social and public health programs. The framework developed in this study provides a flexible and context-oriented approach to evaluating Tehran's ecological resilience. It can serve as a methodologically significant model for cities facing similar challenges, characterized by high population density and limited ecological capacity.

In a reviewing study the concept of urban resilience, Sharifi (2023) points to the growing interest in using the concept of social-ecological-technological systems (SETS) resilience and focuses on nature-based solutions. His study shows that the implementation of the SETS approach leads to several side benefits, including climate change adaptation and mitigation, prevention and response to epidemics, human health and well-being, and justice.

Measuring urban socio-ecological resilience against natural hazards is crucial for sustainable development; in this regard Jaafari et al. (2024) measured the 20-year changes in urban resilience in nine cities of the western province of Iran by selecting, weighting, and prioritizing 31 socioeconomic variables related to natural hazards. In assessing the sustainability of UER networks Zhao et al. (2021) combined DPSIR with an ENA model for 35 major cities in China, by calculating the ideal value for resiliency of urban ecosystems, they were evaluated a decrease in the trend of ecologic resilience in the studied cities, which makes the cities more vulnerable and weakness in their sustainability.

In a study for urban ecological planning with sequential action-based dynamic decision support, Kim and et al. (2024) proposed a novel approach to support decision-makers in developing effective stepwise plans focused on the use of ecological corridors and habitat creation as mitigation measures, for sustainable urban development.

As policy recommendations and urban management tool, various strategies can be presented to address the low urban ecological resilience observed in the central and southern parts of Tehran, which are densely populated and lack green and open spaces. Urban planning and management aspect mostly should use land use planning and zoning systems as well as adaptive governance tools to ease resilience planning, monitoring and assessing it. Develop urban resilience plans that integrate ecological resilience as a core component. These plans should consider climate change adaptation, disaster preparedness, and the restoration of ecological functions. Also, continuously monitor and assess urban ecological resilience using tools like the Loss-Gain Approach. Regular evaluations can inform policy adjustments and ensure the effectiveness of implemented strategies. In light of the findings of this study, which have illuminated the challenges facing urban ecological resilience in the densely populated central and southern areas of Tehran the policy recommendations to mitigate these issues and

bolster the city's capacity to adapt and thrive in the face of environmental stresses, can bounce around Enact regulations requiring the integration of green infrastructure elements into urban development projects in central and southern Tehran. This should include mandates for green roofs, permeable pavements, and the allocation of green spaces within new construction. Also, Community-Led Urban Gardens can be helpful to improve urban green infrastructure as well as local community empowerment. Encourage the establishment of community-led urban gardens and allotment schemes, empowering residents to participate actively in ecological restoration and sustainable food production within their neighborhoods. Additionally, as a part of urban land use and infrastructure planning toward a more resilient city, Sustainable Transportation planning will be recommended. It refers to Prioritize investments in sustainable transportation infrastructure, such as public transit, bike lanes, and pedestrian-friendly pathways, to reduce the environmental footprint of urban mobility.

While this study has contributed valuable insights into the urban ecological resilience of Tehran, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. Firstly, the assessment is based on available data, and data gaps may exist, potentially affecting the accuracy of the results. Additionally, the study does not account for future climate change scenarios, which should be addressed in subsequent research. As this study suggests an assessment framework for urban ecological resilience a Long-Term Monitoring can be Conduct to track changes in urban ecological resilience over time, allowing for the evaluation of the effectiveness of policy interventions. Climate Resilience Assessments Can Incorporate climate change projections into resilience assessments to understand how Tehran's ecological resilience may be influenced by future climate events. Moreover, Explore the interplay between urban ecological resilience and social and economic factors, investigating how community demographics and income disparities may impact resilience outcomes. Undertaking comparative studies with other cities to identify best practices in urban ecological resilience and adapt them to Tehran's unique context can be the other suggestion for future further studies.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Aliakbar Shamsipour: Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Shayesteh Jahanshahi:** Validation, Project administration, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Seyed Sajad Mousavi:** Visualization, Validation, Resources, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Faeze Shoja:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology. **Roghayeh Ansari Golenji:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Safiyeh Tayebi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Seyed Ali Alavi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software. **Ayyoob Sharifi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

Acknowledgement

The authors of this paper would like to express their gratitude to the Department of Environment and Sustainable Development of Tehran Municipality for their financial support in conducting this research. They would also like to acknowledge the Tehran Municipality ICT

Organization for providing the necessary research data.

Appendix 1: Characteristics of interviewed experts

	Field	Education	Age	Gender
1	Urban Planning	PhD	45	Male
2	Urban Planning	PhD	40	Male
3	Urban Planning	PhD	39	Female
4	Geography	PhD	43	Male
5	Geography	PhD	40	Male
6	Geography	PhD	53	Male
7	Geography	PhD	48	Female
8	Geography	PhD	55	Female
9	Geography	M.Sc.	38	Female
10	Urban Ecology	M.Sc.	46	Male
11	Environmental planning	PhD	33	Male
12	Environmental engineering	PhD	45	Female
13	Environmental engineering	PhD	45	Female
14	Environmental engineering	PhD	39	Female
15	Urban climatology	M.Sc.	35	Male
16	Urban climatology	M.Sc.	34	Male
17	Urban climatology	PhD	61	Male
18	Urban climatology	PhD	58	Female
19	Urban climatology	PhD	48	Female
20	Urban environment and public services	PhD	36	Female
21	Urban environment and public services	M.Sc.	34	Female
22	Public policy	PhD	41	Female

References

- Abdoli, I., Ghahroudi Tali, M., & TavakoliNia, J. (2021). Thresholds of environmental physical resilience of Tehran metropolis. *Science Resource Relief*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.32592/jorar.2021.13.1.3>. Thresholds.
- Abedini, A., Aram, F., Khalili, A., & Mirzaei, E. (2022). Recognition and evaluating the indicators of urban resilient by using the network analysis process. *URBAN SCIENCE*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/urbansci6020031>. Vol.Issue.
- Alberti, M., & Marzluff, J. M. (2004). Ecological resilience in urban ecosystems: Linking urban patterns to human and ecological functions. *Urban Ecosystems*, 7, 241–265.
- Alcoforado, M.-J., Andrade, H., Lopes, A., & Vasconcelos, J. (2009). Application of Climatic Guidelines to Urban Planning. The example of Lisbon (Portugal). *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 90, 56–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2008.10.006>
- Allahi, S., Mobin, M., Vafadarnikjoo, A., & Salmon, C. (2015). An integrated AHP-GIS-MCLP method to locate bank branches. In *IIE Annual Conference and Expo 2015* (pp. 1104–1113). June.
- Anelli, D., Tajani, F., & Ranieri, R. (2022). Urban resilience against natural disasters: Mapping the risk with an innovative indicators-based assessment approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 371, Article 133496. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133496>
- Arnold, C. L., & Gibbons, C. J. (1996). Impervious Surface Coverage: The Emergence of a Key Environmental Indicator. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 62(2), 243–258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944369608975688>
- Asadzadeh, A., Khavarian-Garmsir, A. R., Sharifi, A., Salehi, P., & Kötter, T. (2022). Transformative resilience: An overview of its structure, evolution, and trends. *Sustainability*, 14(22). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142215267>. Vol.Issue.
- Astiaso Garcia, D., Bruschi, D., Cinquepalmi, F., & Cumo, F. (2013). An estimation of urban fragmentation of natural habitats: Case studies of the 24 Italian National Parks. *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, 32. <https://doi.org/10.3303/CET1332009>
- Bolloorani, A. D., Shorabeh, S. N., Neysani Samany, N., Mousivand, A., Kazemi, Y., Jaafarzadeh, N., Zahedi, A., & Rabiee, J. (2021). Vulnerability mapping and risk analysis of sand and dust storms in Ahvaz, IRAN. *Environmental Pollution*, 279, Article 116859. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116859>
- Booth, D., & Jackson, C. R. (1997). Urbanization of aquatic systems: degradation thresholds, stormwater detection, and the limits of mitigation. *Journal Of The American Water Resources Association*, 33(5), 1077–1090.
- Bukhari, M. H., da Silva, P. F., Pilz, J., Istanbuluoglu, E., Görüm, T., Lee, J., Karamehic-Muratovic, A., Urmı, T., Soltani, A., Wilopo, W., Qureshi, J. A., Zekan, S., Koonisetty, K. S., Sheishenaly, U., Khan, L., Espinoza, J., Mendoza, E. P., & Haque, U. (2023). Community perceptions of landslide risk and susceptibility: A multi-country study. *Landslides*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10346-023-02027-5>
- Calliari, E., Castellari, S., Davis, M., Linnerooth-Bayer, J., Martin, J., Mysiak, J., Pastor, T., Ramieri, E., Scolobig, A., Sterk, M., Veerkamp, C., Wendling, L., & Zandersen, M. (2022). Building climate resilience through nature-based solutions in Europe: A review of enabling knowledge, finance and governance frameworks. *Climate Risk Management*, 37, Article 100450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2022.100450>. August 2021.
- Cao, Y., Wilkinson, E., Pettinotti, L., Colenbrander, S., & Lovell, E. (2021). An Analytical Review: A Decade of Urban Resilience. <https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zs/kgke326/files/2021-12/UNDP-ODI-An-Analytical-Review-A-Decade-of-Urban-Resilience.pdf>.
- Cardoso, M. A., Brito, R. S., Pereira, C., Gonzalez, A., Stevens, J., & Telhado, M. J. (2020). RAF Resilience Assessment Framework—A Tool to Support Cities' Action Planning. *Sustainability*, 12(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12062349>. Vol.Issue.
- Chelleri, L., Waters, J. J., Olazabal, M., & Minucci, G. (2015). Resilience trade-offs: Addressing multiple scales and temporal aspects of urban resilience. *Environment and Urbanization*, 27(1), 181–198. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956247814550780>
- Chen, X., Jiang, S., Xu, L., Xu, H., & Guan, N. (2023a). Resilience assessment and obstacle factor analysis of urban areas facing waterlogging disasters: A case study of Shanghai, China. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(24), 65455–65469. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-26861-1>
- Chen, X., Yu, L., Lin, W., Yang, F., Li, Y., Tao, J., & Cheng, S. (2023b). Urban resilience assessment from the multidimensional perspective using dynamic Bayesian network: A case study of Fujian Province, China. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 238, Article 109469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2023.109469>
- Churkina, G. (2016). The role of urbanization in the global carbon cycle. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2015.00144>
- Costanza, R. (2020). Valuing natural capital and ecosystem services toward the goals of efficiency, fairness, and sustainability. *Ecosystem Services*, 43, Article 101096. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2020.101096>
- Dakas, V., & Kefi, S. (2022). Ecological resilience: What to measure and how to?. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac5767>.
- Datola, G. (2023). Implementing urban resilience in urban planning: A comprehensive framework for urban resilience evaluation. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 98, Article 104821. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2023.104821>
- DAVIES, R. (2022). Iran – Deadly Floods and Landslides in Tehran Province. Flood List. <https://floodlist.com/asia/iran-floods-tehran-province-july-2022>.
- Delgado-Ramos, G. C., & Guibrunet, L. (2017). Assessing the ecological dimension of urban resilience and sustainability. *International Journal of Urban Sustainable Development*, 9(2), 151–169. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19463138.2017.1341890>
- DESA. (2023). Global Sustainable Development Report (GSDR). <https://sdgs.un.org/gsdrgsd2023>.
- Du, M., Zhang, X., Wang, Y., Tao, L., & Li, H. (2020). An operationalizing model for measuring urban resilience on land expansion. *Habitat International*, 102, Article 102206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2020.102206>
- Farhad F. (2021). Adaptation and mitigation for meeting the climate change through urban plans: Assessing urban development plans of Tehran, Iran. May, 1–17. <http://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202105.0500.v1>.
- Feng, X., Xiu, C., Bai, L., Zhong, Y., & Wei, Y. (2020). Comprehensive evaluation of urban resilience based on the perspective of landscape pattern: A case study of Shenyang city. *Cities*, 104, Article 102722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2020.102722>
- Feofilovs, M., & Romagnoli, F. (2020). Assessment of urban resilience to natural disasters with a system dynamics tool: Case study of Latvian municipality. *Environmental and Climate Technologies*, 24(3), 249–264. <https://doi.org/10.2478/tuctec-2020-0101>

- Fu, S., Liu, J., Wang, J., Tian, J., & Li, X. (2023). Enhancing urban ecological resilience through integrated green technology progress: Evidence from Chinese cities. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-023-29451-3>
- Gonçalves, L. A. P. J., & Ribeiro, P. J. G. (2020). Resilience of urban transportation systems. Concept, characteristics, and methods. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 85, Article 102727. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2020.102727>
- Govindarajulu, D. (2020). Strengthening institutional and financial mechanisms for building urban resilience in India. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 47, Article 101549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdr.2020.101549>
- Hajialiakbari, K., Karimi, M., & Tayebi, S. (2021). Toward a paradigm shift in urban planning in Tehran: Neighborhood development plans. *Civil Engineering and Architecture*, 9(7), 2492–2504. <https://doi.org/10.13189/cea.2021.090733>
- Hassanzadehkermanshahi, K., & Shirovzhan, S. (2022). Measuring urban sustainability over time at national and regional scale for addressing United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 11: Iran and Tehran as case studies. *Sustainability*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14127402>
- Heinzle, C., Robert, B., Hémond, Y., & Serre, D. (2020). Operating urban resilience strategies to face climate change and associated risks: Some advances from theory to application in Canada and France. *Cities*, 104, Article 102762. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2020.102762>
- Hickel, J. (2020). The sustainable development index: Measuring the ecological efficiency of human development in the anthropocene. *Ecological Economics*, 167, Article 106331. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.05.011>
- Homayounfar, M., Muneeppeerakul, R., & Anderies, J. M. (n.d.). Resilience-performance trade-offs in managing social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society*, 27(1), <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12892-270107>
- Irfey, A. M. M., Chau, H. W., Sumaiya, M. M. F., Wai, C. Y., Muttill, N., & Jamei, E. (2023). Sustainable mitigation strategies for urban heat island effects in urban areas. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151410767>
- Jha, A. K., Miner, T. W., & Stanton-Geddes, Z. (2013). Building Urban Resilience. In *Building Urban Resilience*. <https://doi.org/10.1596/32622>
- Kamranzad, F., Memarian, H., & Zare, M. (2020). Earthquake risk assessment for Tehran, Iran. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 9(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi9070430>. Vol.Issue.
- Kharrazi, A., Fath, B. D., & Katzmair, H. (2016). Advancing empirical approaches to the concept of resilience: A critical examination of panarchy, ecological information, and statistical evidence. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 8(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8090935>
- Li, G., Cheng, G., & Wu, Z. (2022). Resilience assessment of urban complex giant systems in Hubei section of the three gorges reservoir area based on multi-source data. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148423>
- Li, G., Kou, C., Wang, Y., & Yang, H. (2020). System dynamics modelling for improving urban resilience in Beijing, China. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 161, Article 104954. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104954>
- Li, W., & Yi, P. (2020). Assessment of city sustainability—Coupling coordinated development among economy, society and environment. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 256, Article 120453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120453>
- Li, Y., Lin, J., Li, Y., & Nyerges, T. (2019). Developing a resilience assessment framework for the Urban Land–Water System. *Land Degradation & Development*, 30(9), 1107–1120. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.3297>
- Linko, I. gov, r, Trump, Benjamin D., & Hynes, W. (2019). Resilience-based Strategies and Policies to Address Systemic Risks. 17-18 September 2019, OECD Conference Centre1, 1–35. [https://www.oecd.org/naec/averting-systemic-collapse/SG-NAEC\(2019\)5_Resilience_strategies.pdf](https://www.oecd.org/naec/averting-systemic-collapse/SG-NAEC(2019)5_Resilience_strategies.pdf)
- Liu, W., & Song, Z. (2020). Review of studies on the resilience of urban critical infrastructure networks. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 193, Article 106617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2019.106617>
- Liu, Z., He, C., Zhou, Y., & Wu, J. (2014). How much of the world's land has been urbanized, really? A hierarchical framework for avoiding confusion. *Landscape Ecology*, 29(5), 763–771. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-014-0034-y>
- Madanipour, A. (2006). Urban planning and development in Tehran. *Cities*, 23(6), 433–438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2006.08.002>
- Maes, M. J. A., Jones, K. E., Toledano, M. B., & Milligan, B. (2019). Mapping synergies and trade-offs between urban ecosystems and the sustainable development goals. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 93, 181–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.12.010>
- Marzluff, J. M. (2001). Worldwide urbanization and its effects on birds BT - Avian Ecology and Conservation in an Urbanizing World (J. M. Marzluff, R. Bowan, & R. Donnelly (eds.); pp. 19–47). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4615-1531-9_2
- Mashayekhi, A. (2019). The 1968 Tehran master plan and the politics of planning development in Iran (1945–1979). *Planning Perspectives*, 34(5), 849–876. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02665433.2018.1468805>
- McGill, R. (2020). Urban resilience – An urban management perspective. *Journal of Urban Management*, 9(3), 372–381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jum.2020.04.004>
- Meerow, S., Newell, J. P., & Stults, M. (2016). Defining urban resilience: A review. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 147, 38–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2015.11.011>
- Mironova, E., Volkova, I., Gura, D., & Makar, S. (2022). Fragmentation of natural habitats by urban development at Sochi. *International Journal of Environmental Studies*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207233.2022.2057703>
- Modrzyński, P., & Karaszewski, R. (2022). Urban energy management—a systematic literature review. *ENERGIES*, 15(21). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15217848>. Vol.Issue.
- Moghbel, M., & Shamsipour, A. A. (2019). Spatiotemporal characteristics of urban land surface temperature and UHI formation: A case study of Tehran, Iran. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 137(3–4), 2463–2476. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-018-2735-7>
- OECD G20. (2021). Towards a more resource-efficient and circular economy. I, Paris: OECD Publishing (pp. 1–53).
- Phillips, Y. A., Kouikoglou, V. S., & Verdugo, C. (2017). Urban sustainability assessment and ranking of cities. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 64, 254–265. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2017.03.002>
- Potenza, G., Gerardi, G., Fascetti, S., & Rosati, L. (2022). Habitat fragmentation and lichen diversity in Peri-Urban Woodlands: A case study in the municipality of Potenza (Southern Italy). *Plants*, 11(14). <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11141858>. Vol.Issue.
- Qiao, Z., Lu, Y., He, T., Wu, F., Xu, X., Liu, L., Wang, F., Sun, Z., & Han, D. (2023). Spatial expansion paths of urban heat islands in Chinese cities: Analysis from a dynamic topological perspective for the improvement of climate resilience. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 188, Article 106680. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2022.106680>
- Rabbani, G., Kardani-Yazd, N., & Mansouri Daneshvar, M. R. (2020). Factors affecting severe weather threat index in urban areas of Turkey and Iran. *Environmental Systems Research*, 9(1), 9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40068-020-00173-6>
- Ren, C., Ng, E. Y. Y., & Katschnner, L. (2011). Urban climatic map studies: A review. *International Journal of Climatology*, 31(15), 2213–2233. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.2237>
- Ren, C., Spit, T., Lenzholzer, S., Yim, H. L. S., Heusinkveld, B., Hove, B.van, Chen, L., Kupskif, S., Burghardt, R., & Katschnner, L. (2012). Urban climate map system for Dutch spatial planning. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 18, 207–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2012.01.026>
- Saif, J., Wright, A., Khattak, S., & Elfadli, K. (2021). Keeping cool in the desert: Using wind catchers for improved thermal comfort and indoor air quality at half the energy. *Buildings*, 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings11030100>. Vol.Issue.
- Sharifi, A. (2019). Urban form resilience: A meso-scale analysis. *Cities*, 93, 238–252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2019.05.010>
- Sharifi, A. (2021). Urban sustainability assessment: An overview and bibliometric analysis. *Ecological Indicators*, 121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.107102>
- Sharifi, A. (2023). Resilience of urban social-ecological-technological systems (SETS): A review. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 99, Article 104910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2023.104910>
- Sharifi, A., & Yamagata, Y. (2016). Urban resilience assessment: Multiple dimensions, criteria, and indicators. *Advanced Sciences and Technologies for Security Applications*, 259–276. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-39812-9_13. October 2017.
- Shen, L., Kyylo, J. M., & Guo, X. L. (2013). An integrated model based on a hierarchical indices system for monitoring and evaluating urban sustainability. *Sustainability*, 5(2), 524–559. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su5020524>. WE - Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED) WE - Social Science Citation Index (SSCI).
- Shi, C., Zhu, X., Wu, H., & Li, Z. (2022). Assessment of urban ecological resilience and its influencing factors: A case study of the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei Urban agglomeration of China. *Land*, 11(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11060921>. Vol.Issue.
- St. George Freeman, S., Brown, C., Cañada, H., Martinez, V., Palma Nava, A., Ray, P., Rodriguez, D., Romo, A., Tracy, J., Vázquez, E., Wi, S., & Boltz, F. (2020). Resilience by design in Mexico City: A participatory human-hydrologic systems approach. *Water Security*, 9, Article 100053. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasec.2019.100053>
- Suárez, M., Gómez-Baggethun, E., Benayas, J., & Tilbury, D. (2016). Towards an urban resilience index: A case study in 50 Spanish cities. *Sustainability*, 8, 774. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8080774>
- Sundstrom, S. M., Angeler, D. G., Bell, J., Hayes, M., Hodbod, J., Jalalzadeh-Fard, B., Mahmood, R., VanWormer, E., & Allen, C. R. (2023). Panarchy theory for convergence. *Sustainability Science*, 18(4), 1667–1682. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01299-z>
- Tayebi, S., Alavi, S. A., Esfandi, S., Meshkani, L., & Shamsipour, A. (2023). Evaluation of Land Use Efficiency in Tehran's Expansion between 1986 and 2021 : Developing an Assessment Framework Using DEMATEL and Interpretive Structural Modeling Methods.
- Tayebi, S., Esfandi, S., Bahraini Moqadam, S., & Sharifi, A. (2022a). Investigating the role of neighborhood development offices (NDOs) in the resilience of deteriorated urban neighborhoods against the COVID-19 pandemic: An empirical study of Tehran, using a hybrid balanced-based assessment framework. *Urban Science*, 6(4), 77. <https://doi.org/10.3390/urbansci6040077>
- Tayebi, S., Feizizadeh, B., Esfandi, S., Aliabassi, B., Ali Alavi, S., & Shamsipour, A. (2022b). A neighborhood-based urban water carrying capacity assessment: analysis of the relationship between spatial-demographic factors and water consumption patterns in Tehran, Iran. *Land*, 11(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11122203>
- Tayebi, S., Mohammadi, H., Shamsipour, A., Tayebi, S., Alavi, S. A., & Hoseinioun, S. (2019). Analysis of land surface temperature trend and climate resilience challenges in Tehran. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 16(12), 8585–8594. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-019-02329-z>
- Ullah, H., Akbar, M., & Khan, F. (2020). Construction of homogeneous climatic regions by combining cluster analysis and L-moment approach on the basis of reconnaissance drought index for Pakistan. *International Journal of Climatology*, 40(1), 324–341. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.6214>
- UNDP. (2006). Disaster Risk Management Profile Tehran, Iran (pp. 1–19).
- United Nation-HLPP. (2018). 2018 Review of SDGs Implementation : SDG 11 – Make Cities and Human Settlements Inclusive, Safe, Resilient and Sustainable. In High-Level Political Forum on Sustainable Development (p. 11).
- UNO. (2018). World Urbanization Prospects. In Demographic Research (Vol. 12). <https://population.un.org/wup/Publications/Files/WUP2018-Report.pdf>
- Vitale, C., Meijerink, S., Moccia, F. D., & Ache, P. (2020). Urban flood resilience, a discursive-institutional analysis of planning practices in the Metropolitan City of

- Milan. *Land Use Policy*, 95, Article 104575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104575>
- Wang, X., Van Dam, K., Triantafyllidis, C., Koppelaar, R., & Shah, N. (2017). Water and energy systems in sustainable city development: A case of Sub-Saharan Africa. *Procedia Engineering*, 198, 948–957. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.07.140>
- Wang, Y., Cai, Y., Xie, Y., Chen, L., & Zhang, P. (2023). An integrated approach for evaluating dynamics of urban eco-resilience in urban agglomerations of China. *Ecological Indicators*, 146, Article 109859. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.109859>
- Wardekker, A., Wilk, B., Brown, V., Uittenbroek, C., Mees, H., Driessen, P., Wassen, M., Molenaar, A., Walda, J., & Runhaar, H. (2020). A diagnostic tool for supporting policymaking on urban resilience. *Cities*, 101, Article 102691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2020.102691>
- World Bank. (2023). Urban population. World Bank. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.URB.TOTL?end=2021&start=1960&view=chart>.
- Yamagata, Y., & Sharifi, A. (2018). No Title. In Y. Yamagata & A. Sharifi (Eds.), *Resilience-Oriented Urban Planning*. Springer Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-75798-8>.
- Yang, M., Jiao, M., & Zhang, J. (2022). Research on urban resilience and influencing factors of Chengdu-Chongqing economic circle. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(17). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141710585>
- You, X., Sun, Y., & Liu, J. (2022). Evolution and analysis of urban resilience and its influencing factors: A case study of Jiangsu Province, China. *Natural Hazards*, 113(3), 1751–1782. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-022-05368-x>
- Zambrano, L., Aronson, M. F. J., & Fernandez, T. (2019). The consequences of landscape fragmentation on socio-ecological patterns in a rapidly developing urban area: A case study of the national autonomous university of Mexico. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2019.00152>. Vol.
- Zhang, J., Wang, S., Pradhan, P., Zhao, W., & Fu, B. (2022). Untangling the interactions among the sustainable development goals in China. *Science Bulletin*, 67(9), 977–984. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2022.01.006>
- Zhao, R., Fang, C., Liu, H., & Liu, X. (2021). Evaluating urban ecosystem resilience using the DPSIR framework and the ENA model: A case study of 35 cities in China. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 72, Article 102997. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2021.102997>
- Zheng, F., Xiao, C., You, Z., Feng, & Zhiming. (2022). Evaluating the resources and environmental carrying capacity in Laos using a three-dimensional tetrahedron model. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(13618). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192113816>